

New sighting records of the white throated thrush *Zoothera citrina cyanotus* from southern Maharashtra

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White throated thrush is inhabited in evergreen and deciduous forest singly or in 2-3 individual groups on damp, shady forest floor and, on lower branches of small trees/shrubs (Ali, 2002; Grimmett *et al.*, 2011). It is a rare, resident, shy and locally migratory bird migrating during monsoon in India from south eastern Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh and south Orissa to Tamil Nadu and Kerala (Ali, 2002; Grimmett *et al.*, 1998). The bird is reported from Rajasthan (Bhardwaj & Sangha, 2008), Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Bihar, Andra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala and Maharashtra (Grewal *et al.*, 2002; Pande *et al.*, 2003; references in Bhardwaj & Sangha, 2008). In Maharashtra bird is reported from evergreen jungles of Mahabaleshwar in Satara district (Pandy, 1979). Mahabal & Lamba (1987) also sighted the bird from Maharashtra (reference in Prasad, 2003). Thereafter, there are no reports of its sighting in Maharashtra. In this note we report new sighting records of the white throated thrush from different parts of Chandgad taluk in Kolhapur district of southern Maharashtra and for the first time from Kolhapur. *Zoothera citrina* is evaluated as a least concerned bird and its population declining in recent years due to loss or fragmentation of woodland poses a threat to forest birds (IUCN, 2013; Wikipedia, 2013).

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During our routine field work surprisingly we encountered single male white throated thrush *Zoothera citrina cyanotus* (Figure-1) on the forest floor of Vaghotre village near Chandgad (15° 55' 60 N, 74° 12' 0 E). By opportunistic sighting method we sighted the bird on 21st, November 2011 at 14:30 hrs foraging on the leaf litter of forest floor at least for 2 minutes. Then the bird flies on branches of small tree about 1 meter height from the ground. It was there on the tree branches for some time jumping from a branch to other for another 2-3 minutes and flew to disappear in the forest. The bird measures around 22 cm. Head and under parts yellowish brown. Neck, throat and ear coverts are white. A pair of black oblique banding pattern is diagnostic starts from the base of eye and extends back below the eye for shorter distance through ear coverts. Rest of the above part and wings are slaty blue in color. A diagnostic white patch is found on both sides of the wings on dorsal side.

White throated thrush is quite regularly sighted (Figure-2) by ASL viz. in dense forest of Bhimashankar on December 11th, 2006 at 14:11 hrs in Pune district; in dense vegetation of Amba reserved forest (November 9th, 2008 at 9:30 hrs; November 6th, 13th, 2010; February 16th, 2011), in Palasamba forest on February 28th, 2011 and in different parts of the Chandgad forest (December 13th, 20th, 2010; November 18th, 26th, 27th, 2011; December 6th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 17th, 2011) between 9:00 to 16:30 hrs in Kolhapur district. NCH sighted 2 and 3 individual birds in Tillari forest floor on 4th and 5th, February 2012 respectively in two different places; 2 individuals in Tudiye forest floor on 28th, April 2012; 2 individuals in Mahalunge forest on 29th, April 2012 and single bird in Yashwantrao Chavan college campus Halkarni on 30th, April 2012 in Chandgad taluk. These sightings indicate that, white throated

thrush found as winter visitor/resident in Chandgad taluk of Kolhapur in southern Maharashtra. It seems that, *Zoothera citrina cyanotus* using southern Maharashtra as migratory route or habitat during their migration towards Tamil Nadu and Kerala.

Figure-1. White throated thrush sited on the forest floor of Vaghotre

Figure-2..White throated thrush sited in dense vegetation of Amba

2. Bhardwaj, G. S. and Sangha, H. S. 2008. Orange-headed Thrush *Zoothera citrina cyanotus* a first record for Rajasthan. *Indian Birds*. 4 (1): 19.
3. Grewal, B., Harvey, B. and Pfister O. 2002. A Photographic guide to the Birds of India and Indian subcontinent, including Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and the Maldives. Princeton University Press, New Jersey.
4. Grimmett, R., Inskipp, C. and Inskipp, T. 1998. Birds of the Indian subcontinent. Christopher Helm, Oxford University Press, New Delhi.
5. Grimmett, R., Inskipp, C. and Inskipp, T. 2011. Birds of the Indian subcontinent IInd edn. Christopher Helm, Oxford University Press, India. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orange-headed_Thrush downloaded on 20 September 2013
6. IUCN 2013. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2013.1. <www.iucnredlist.org>. Downloaded on 20 September 2013.
7. Panday, D. J. 1979. Courtship song and display of the Whitethroated ground Thrush *Zoothera citrina cyanotus* (Jardine and Selby). *J. Bombay Nat. Hist. Soc.*, 76: 365-366.
8. Pande, S. A., Tambe, S., Francis, M. C. and Sant, N. 2003. Birds of Western Ghats, Kokan and Malabar (Including Birds of Goa). 1st edn. Mumbai: Bombay Natural History Society, Oxford University Press
9. Prasad, A. 2003. Annotated checklist of the Birds of Western Maharashtra. *Buceros*. 8 (2 and 3): 3-174.

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Conflict of Interests:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Ali, S. 2002. The book of Indian birds, 13th edition, Bombay Natural History Society, Bombay.